
The Influence of the Seasonality Factor in Increasing the Range of Services Provided By Placement Media

Abiyev Jakhongir
Makhmudova Aziza
PhDs of SamIES

Abstract. *The seasonality factor occupies a special place in the development of the hotel economy. The seasonality factor has a huge impact on the functioning of any placement Enterprise, since, Hotels, first of all, it is possible to distinguish three groups of factors that are influenced by tourist flows visiting the destination: natural climatic factors: the specificity of the tourism net; the specificity of the cocktail and the features of Consumer Recreation.*

Keywords: *tourists, tourism, guests, hotels, motels.*

INTRODUCTION

The period when the number of visiting tourists in a month exceeds the average number for the whole year is accepted as a season for one or another tourist region. In situations where there are two seasons (mostly summer and winter), there is a period between them known as interseason. The period of the year with the highest number of visitors is called the "hot season", and the period when tourists are not visited is called the "dead season".

If we look at seasonality in more detail, then we can talk about five seasons during the year. The height of the season (peak) is observed for a short period of time - in most cases, one or two weeks of the summer season. For him, the destination is characterized by the maximum flow of tourists. The peak of the season usually occurs during the high season. This ensures the flow of tourists to the destination and lasts from two to three weeks to three to four months in different regions of the world.

In many regions of the world, there is a period known as the inter-seasonal period, which corresponds to the spring and autumn seasons of the year. For such a time, the destination is characterized by a low flow of tourists and specialization in certain types of tourist activities. For example, the inter-season allows for the development of medical, sports, extreme, educational, professional, scientific tourism, but always denies the possibility of organizing beach-bathing tourism.

In the winter season of the year, there is a decrease or decrease in the tourist flow, therefore it starts as the blue or low season. A "buyer's market" begins, as hotel service providers reduce prices to the minimum level to attract an additional flow of tourists. With this, all blue seasons are relative concepts

of a high level, because during this period there is an opportunity to develop winter types of tourism: sports, mountain - skiing, extreme, adventure, treatment, etc.

Within the blue season, a "dead season" is distinguished (for 2 - 3 weeks), during which the flow of tourists to the destination is almost non-existent, therefore, many hotel enterprises specializing in tourism from the state and regions are at a loss (loss). works. But only the correct policy of the hotel and positive relations with travel agencies will allow to attract tourists to the destination during the dead season. As an example of the negative consequences of seasonality, it is possible to cite the fact that in the main part of the year, the main seats in hotels are almost not in demand. In order to attract tourists in the off-season or to develop the winter season, accommodation companies are forced to apply a flexible policy or introduce new services.

Season extension (expansion) allows business to provide services - organization of conferences, seminars and meetings.

The existence of a seasonality factor in the activity of the tourism industry of our country is explained by the climatic conditions of Uzbekistan and the fact that natural and climatic factors play an important role in the formation of agricultural products. This is especially evident in the example of the tourism system of the Samarkand region, which is a tourist destination. In terms of domestic tourism, tourists traveled mainly in February 5.2%, June 19% and August 15.1%. 10.7% and 18.3% of visitors visited inbound tourism mainly in April and May, while in December, January, February and March this figure was only 1.8%.

Based on their capabilities, the tourists of our country spend their holidays mainly in the summer months, and the volume of trips in these months corresponds to 42.8%. The focus is mainly on family vacations - the 2-fold decrease in the number of trips in September is explained by the beginning of the school year, the average family trip is made with a family consisting of 3 people.

The following are the main reasons for this situation:

- strive to divide the vacation time into parts and make several trips during the year (including on holidays);
- shortening of vacation duration for many in new labor relations and the impossibility of leaving "direct duty, work" for a long time (more than two weeks);
- the limitation of the ability to pay, because the cost of popular tours is 500-700 \$ per person.

The duration of the trips is coordinated with the purpose of the tours. For example, trips related to leisure, active recreation and tourism (the leading type of motivation) tend to be short-term, while cruises and medical trips tend to be long-term. Thus, it is clear that consumers-tourists prefer to use a tourist product whose program is enriched with content and provides the opportunity to make a great impression and result in a short period of time.

This, in turn, requires the re-transformation of the tourism and hotel industry, and the adaptation of tourist programs and their periods to world standards of service.

We recommend the following additional methods to deal with seasonality:

Solving the problem through a flexible pricing policy, which includes demand-based pricing, various discounts and bonuses, and a loyalty program.

Increasing the range of services, as well as increasing the volume of services in all departments.

Introducing special package rates for certain groups of customers, such as business customers (accommodation+transfer or accommodation+lunch and dinner) or weekend customers (accommodation+excursions), as well as groups with tourist companies to conclude preferential contracts for

Congress services, i.e. organization of conferences, seminars, meetings, as well as weddings and other celebrations at special prices outside the "high" season.

Development of restaurant services. The role of restaurant services in increasing the range of services is incomparable, that is, receiving customers through discounts in off-season periods.

References:

1. Gulmira, T., Sobirov, B., Suyunovich, T. I., & Hasanovna, A. D. Implementation Of Up-To-Date Innovative Approaches In A Competitive Merit Of Tourism Industry In Central Asia. The Case Of Uzbekistan. *Journal of Management Value & Ethics*, 4.
2. Gulmira, T., Sobirov, B., Suyunovich, T. I., & Hasanovna, A. D. Implementation Of Up-To-Date Innovative Approaches In A Competitive Merit Of Tourism Industry In Central Asia. The Case Of Uzbekistan. *Journal of Management Value & Ethics*, 4.
3. Tuxhliev, I. S., Hayitboev, R., Safarov, B. S., & Tursunova, G. R. (2014). Basics of tourism. Textbook. Ministry of Higher and Secondary Special Education of the Republic of Uzbekistan.-T.:. *Science and technology*, 151.
4. Тухлиев, И. С., Бабаев, Ф., & Махмудова, А. (2017). Основные задачи дальнейшего развития туристической отрасли Узбекистана. *Индустрия туризма: возможности, приоритеты, проблемы и перспективы*, 10(1), 391-398.
5. Болтабаев, М. Р., Тухлиев, И. С., Сафаров, Б. Ш., & Абдурахимов, С. А. (2018). Туризм: теория и практика. *Т.: Fan va texnologiya*.
6. Suyunovich, T. I., & Pirmamatovna, M. A. (2023). Use of Digital Technologies Is Becoming One of the Main Tasks of the Tourism Industry. *Web of Scholars: Multidimensional Research Journal*, 2(6), 134-137.
7. Sadibekova, B., Makhmudova, A., Abdukhamidov, S., & Mukhamadiev, A. (2021). The main forms of pilgrimage tourism. *CENTRAL ASIAN JOURNAL OF INNOVATIONS ON TOURISM MANAGEMENT AND FINANCE*, 2 (2), 84-88.
8. Abdukhamidov, A. S., & Makhmudova, A. P. (2022). Prospects for the development of recreational tourism in Uzbekistan. *Builders Of The Future*, 2(02), 31-38.
9. Makhmudova, A. (2019). Enhancement of the Ecotourism Efficiency in the Republic of Uzbekistan: Experience of the Developed Countries. *Indonesian Journal of Law and Economics Review*, 3, 10-21070.
10. Makhmudova, A. (2020). Organizational and economic reasons preventing the development of ecological tourism in Uzbekistan. *Journal of Advanced Research in Dynamical and Control Systems*, 12(6), 1217-1220.
11. Erkin, G., & Elena, S. (2023). THE IMPORTANCE OF DESTINATIONS FOR TOURISM SPHERE. *Best Journal of Innovation in Science, Research and Development*, 2(9), 402-406.
12. Erkin, G., & Odilov, A. (2023). THE IMPORTANCE OF THE TOURISM INDUSTRY FOR ECONOMIC DEVELOPMENT. *Best Journal of Innovation in Science, Research and Development*, 2(10), 412-416.
13. Irgashevich, S. T., Odilovich, O. A., & Mamadaliyevich, G. E. (2022). Internet Technologies In The Tourism Industry. *Web of Scientist: International Scientific Research Journal*, 3(9), 57-64.
14. Elena, S. (2023). Importance of Events for Tourism Management. *Pioneer: Journal of Advanced Research and Scientific Progress*, 2(4), 119-123.

15. Erkayeva, G., & Vayskulov, R. (2022). Mintaqaviy turizmni rivojlantirishda geoaxborot texnologiyalarning ahamiyat.“. *Iqtisodiyot va innovatsion texnologiyalar*”(Economics and Innovative Technologies) ilmiy elektron jurnali, 1, 344-352.
16. Erkayeva, G., & Vayskulov, R. (2022). TURIZM SALOHİYATINI RIVOJLANTIRISHDA MOBIL INNOVATSION TEXNOLOGIYALARDAN SAMARALI FOYDALANISH YO ‘LLARI. *Economics and Innovative Technologies*, 10(5), 348-356.
17. Fayzullaevich, K. G., Panjiyevna, E. G., & Gaybulla o‘g‘li, F. K. (2021). LABOR MOTIVATION IN SMALL BUSINESS ENTERPRISES. *American Journal of Economics and Business Management*, 4(2), 89-93.